

Insect viruses found in the Philippines. IRRI.

Host	Common name	Virus disease ^a	Shape of inclusion bodies	Host plant found	Collection data	
					Date	Place
<i>Mythimna separata</i> (Walker) ^b	Armyworm	NPV	Tetragonal	Rice	Aug 1985	IRRI
<i>Spodoptera litura</i> (Fab.)	Common cutworm	NPV	Tetragonal	Rice, taro	Jul 1985	IRRI
<i>Herpetogramma licarsisalis</i> (Walker)	Grass webworm	NPV	Hexagonal	Rice	Sep 1984	South Cotabato
<i>Mocis frugalis</i> (Fab.) ^c	Rice brown semilooper	GV	Ellipsoidal	Rice	Jul 1985	Palawan
<i>Cnaphalocrocis medinalis</i> (Guenée)	Rice leaffolder	GV	Ellipsoidal	Rice	Oct 1985	IRRI

^aNPV = nuclear polyhedrosis virus, GV = granulosis virus. ^b New species found in the Philippines. ^c New recorded virus disease of the host insect.

Light and electron micrographs showing the following: nuclear polyhedra isolated from *M. separata* (1a), *S. litura* (1b), and *H. licarsisalis* (1c); granular capsules of *C. medinalis* (1d) and *M. frugalis* (1e), with some abnormal forms (arrow); and virions of *S. litura* polyhedra after treatment with weak alkali for 30 min (1f).

or artificial diets to determine incidence of virus diseases. Specimens were examined under the light and phase contrast microscope. Virus particles were examined with the electron microscope.

Three species of nuclear polyhedrosis viruses (NPV) and two species of granulosis viruses (GV) were found (see table). The behavior of infected larvae was characteristic of most virus-infected insects: they become sluggish and cease

feeding a few days after infection.

As the diseases progressed, a watery fluid exuding from the mouth of the larvae *S. litura* changed from colorless to a pale tint to pink. Most larvae infected with NPV hung from their host plant by attaching the second abdominal legs to the plants. In late stages of the disease, the cuticle ruptured, releasing a milky white fluid. *Mocis frugalis* larvae infected with GV were yellow with shrunken abdominal segments. The

larvae slowly darkened, but the integument remained tough and leathery.

Shape and size of polyhedra in different insect hosts varied (see figure). Polyhedra in *Mythimna separata* Walker and *Spodoptera litura* (Fab.) were tetragon mixed with triangular shapes. Polyhedra from *Herpetogramma licarsisalis* (Walker) were hexagonal. Capsules of GV of *Mocis frugalis* (Fab.) and *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée) were ellipsoidal. Some capsules in *M. frugalis* were irregular and sickle-shaped. The rod-shaped virion of *M. frugalis* granulosis were embedded singly in capsules, but polyhedra of *S. litura* were multi-embedded.

Size of polyhedra were $2.12 \pm 0.51 \mu\text{m}$ from *S. litura*; $1.87 \pm 0.24 \mu\text{m}$ from *M. separata*, and $1.37 \pm 0.17 \mu\text{m}$ from *H. licarsisalis*. Capsule size was $433 \pm 15.4 \text{ nm}$ long and $242.7 \pm 17.4 \text{ nm}$ wide in *M. frugalis*, and $412.9 \pm 31.4 \text{ nm}$ long and $234.1 \pm 17.4 \text{ nm}$ wide in *C. medinalis*. □

Weed hosts of rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera* Olivier (Coleoptera: Hispidae)

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Rice hispa beetles sometimes infest weeds and wheat. We studied the suitability of some common weeds as hosts of rice hispa in 1985-86.

Table 1. Rice hispa beetle feeding and development on some common weeds. BRRI, Gazipur, Bangladesh, 1985.

Host	Feeding damage ^a	Eggs deposited	Grub development (%)
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	3	Few	0
<i>Digitaria ciliaris</i>	9	Few	0
<i>Digitaria setigera</i>	9	Few	0
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	9	Few	0
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	9	Few	0
<i>Eleusine indica</i>	9	Few	0
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	9	Few	0
Rice (BR3)	9	Many	>50%

^a 0 to 9 scale: 0 = no damage, 9 = more than 50% leaves damaged.

Seven weed species and rice variety BR3 (30-d-old plants) were grown in 15-cm clay pots. Each pot was infested with 4 greenhouse-reared, mated, hispa females and enclosed in mylar film cages for 7 d. Exposed plants were sprinkled with water daily for grub development. Feeding damage was graded on a 0 to 9 scale.

The beetles laid numerous eggs on rice, but few on weeds (Table 1). Grubs died at the 1st- or 2d-instar stage on weeds, but more than 50% developed into pupae on rice. Feeding damage on

Cyperus rotundus was minimal (damage grade 3) and no grubs developed. All other weeds and rice were heavily damaged.

It appears that, while rice hispa may use weeds as alternate food sources, it cannot complete its life cycle on them.

In a separate experiment, 30-d-old plants of rice (BR3), wheat (Barkat), maize (JC-2), and 9 species of weeds were grown separately in 15-cm clay pots enclosed in fine mesh wire net rectangular cages, with 4 replications. Greenhouse-reared hispa beetles were

Table 2. Preference of rice hispa beetles for rice, wheat, maize, and some common weeds. BRRI, Gazipur, Bangladesh, 1986.

Host	Beetles settling on plants (%)
Rice (BR3)	24.2 a
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	19.2 ab
<i>Eleusine indica</i>	14.2 bc
<i>Scirpus maritimus</i>	9.0 cd
<i>Digitaria ciliaris</i>	8.3 d
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	8.0 d
<i>Paspalum distichum</i>	7.2 d
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i>	2.7 e
Maize (JC-2)	2.7 e
<i>Commelina benghalensis</i>	2.4 e
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	1.3 e
Wheat (Barkat)	0.7 e

starved for 3 h and released at 100 beetles/cage. Beetles that settled on plants were counted 48 h after infestation.

Rice was the most preferred site (24% beetles settled), followed by *Echinochloa colona* (19%) and *Eleusine indica* (14%) (Table 2). Wheat was least preferred. Hispa beetles probably disperse to other plants when the available rice canopy is inadequate to support their numbers. □

Effect of parasitization on food consumption of rice leaffolder (LF) *Marasmia patnalis*

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The amount of food the LF, an important defoliator of the rice plant, consumes during feeding affects yields. But when LF is parasitized, the amount of leaf tissue consumed changes.

LF parasitoids are abundant in ricefields. *Copidomopsis nacoletiae*, a parasitoid of egg and larvae, and *Goniozus triangulifer*, a parasitoid of LF larvae, are important mortality factors for LF in the Philippines.

We studied the influence of parasitism by *C. nacoletiae* on LF food consumption. Ten newly laid LF eggs were exposed for 24 h in tubes containing colonies of the parasitoid.

The hatch was reared individually in tubes with cut leaves from 60-d-old rice variety IR64. Leaves were changed every 24 h until LF larvae ceased feeding and mummified. The area of leaf consumed was measured on graph paper.

In another experiment, 20 newly hatched LF larvae were reared individually in tubes with cut leaves of rice variety IR64. Leaves were changed daily. When the larvae reached the 4th instar, 10 were placed individually in tubes containing pairs of *G. triangulifer*. After parasitization, the larvae were returned to their original tube containing cut rice leaf until they stopped feeding.

The leaf area consumed was measured on graph paper. LF parasitized by *C. nacoletiae* consumed more food than unparasitized LF. The lowest food consumption was by larvae parasitized by *G. triangulifer* (see figure). *C. nacoletiae*-parasitized larvae fed for 16.4

d; *G. triangulifer*-parasitized larvae fed 13.9 d; and unparasitized larvae fed 15.2 d.

The number of live larvae and the percentage of damaged leaves are the bases for deciding to spray LF with insecticide. Presence or absence of either parasitoid might influence an integrated control program. □

Influence of parasitization by *C. nacoletiae* and *G. triangulifer* on leaf consumption by LF.